

HARMONICS MITIGATION OF P&O MPPT BASED SOLAR POWERED NEUTRAL POINT CLAMPED MULTILEVEL INVERTER

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ABSTRACT

To supplement the power shortages, renewable energy sources are a promising source among the existing resources of energy out of which solar PV (photo voltaic) is most popular due to its significant advantages. Controlling the output of solar PV system and harmonics at the load end are key aspects. The main theme of this paper is to control output of solar PV system with MPPT (maximum power point tracking) and reduction of harmonics at the load end. In this paper, commercial solar arrays of 1.2 kW along with P&O (perturb and observe) MPPT to track maximum power has been interfaced with neutral point clamped multilevel inverter. Simulation has been done for different level with the aim to reduce THD (total harmonic distortion) at the load end. Modeling and simulation of solar PV system and DC-DC boost converter has been done using SIMSCAPE library of MATLAB and the output of Boost Converter has been interfaced with neutral point clamped multilevel inverter which has been modeled in SIMULINK library of MATLAB. The advantage of using SIMSCAPE library is that it models the system considering all the physical effects. The output of solar cell has been interfaced with the boost converter. Once the system is modeled in SIMSCAPE it can be easily implemented on hardware for real-time application.

KEYWORDS

Solar panels, MPPT, DC-DC boost converter, continuous conduction mode (CCM), Neutral Point Clamped Multilevel Inverter

1. NOMENCLATURE

e	Electron charge (1.602×10^{-19} C)
k	Boltzmann constant
I	Cell output current
I_{ph}	Photon generated current
I_0	Reverse saturation current for diode D
I_{02}	Reverse saturation current for diode D2
R_s	Series resistance of cell
R_{sh}	Shunt resistance of cell
V	Cell output voltage
V_t	Thermal voltage = $V_T = (N_s \cdot N \cdot k \cdot T) / q$

T	Cell operating temperature
$P_{in,max}$	Maximum power obtain from solar PV
V_{pv}	Voltage of solar PV for maximum power
Δ	Percentage of ripple current to load output current
$I_{out(max)}$	Maximum output current
ΔV_{out}	Desired output voltage ripple
F_s	Switching frequency
D	Duty cycle
$V_{pv,max}$	Maximum output voltage from PV array
ΔI_L	Desired ripple Current
V_{in}	Input voltage of the boost converter
V_{out}	Average output voltage of the boost converter
t_{on}	Switching on time of the MOSFET
t_{off}	Switching off time of MOSFET
η	Efficiency of the converter
V_{in}	Input voltage of the boost converter
t_{off}	Switching off time of MOSFET
Q	Charge on an electron
N	Diode emission coefficient or quality factor of the diode
$N2$	Diode emission coefficient or quality factor of the diode D2.
M	Modulation Index

2. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays most demanding Renewable energy sources such as photovoltaic (PV) and fuel cells (FC), wind energy requires power electronic conditioning. Recently the PV system installation is growing rapidly due to its major concerns related to environment, global warming, energy security, technology improvements and decreasing costs. Energy generated from PV system is being considered as clean and eco-friendly sources of energy [5].

Photovoltaic is the most convenient and promising renewable energy due its abundant quantity available in nature, it is gaining more attention during the last several years as a source of energy. The main disadvantage of PV system are the high cost of installation of solar panels and lower conversion efficiency. But With the help of newer techniques of manufacturing crystalline design, it is possible to make the PV system cost effective. PV energy system will have more impact in the future due to the development of economic power conversion equipment [1].

From previous research [3], it has been shown that out of all energy sources mainly PV can be easily integrate with existing topology of switched mode DC-DC power converters. Normally a solar panel which is consisting 36 cells in series will only produce approximately 21V in maximum sunlight condition and the maximum power production from the panel will be limited to only few hours for charging the batteries of 12V [8]. Generally Solar panels are

designed in such a manner to have output voltage of about 23-38 V at maximum power point (MPP) and rated power around 160 W at a radiation level of 1000 W/m^2 . In the next stage solar panels are connected to DC-DC converter. This stage is also responsible for tracking the maximum power with the help of maximum power point algorithm and keeping the output remain synchronized with loads[7]

A DC-DC boost converter can be controlled by PWM control and this technique will be applied between the solar panel and the batteries, in order to boost up the voltage of solar panel to charge the batteries at any time even when the panel voltage is less than battery charging voltage. Although the initial cost of solar cell is very high, Role of DC-DC boost converter is important for solving this situation [5].

Due to this reason power electronics devices have been become an indispensable part for renewable energy systems (RES). So for obtaining desired voltage level, boost converter employed which increases the generated solar panels voltage and inverter converts the DC in to an AC. Another methods can be used as Multilevel Inverter (MLI)[4-6] .

Solar simulator can be used as testing for any maximum power point algorithm or Power-Voltage (P-V) or Voltage Current (V-I) or any characteristic of PV solar panel in any weather condition.

Before stepping towards power electronics system, it is required to think about the PV panels design corresponding to load. Based on the assigned load it is required to decide what will be the numbers of cells required to be connected in series or parallel as per the requirement. So the requirement of PV simulator is essential to evaluate the performance of PV system along with electronics devices under various environmental conditions.

The power electronics can be used in this work for improving the harmonics profile at the load end i.e. MLI as MLI replaces the use the conventional two level inverter which reduce total harmonic distortion (THD) that is reason why it is being more popular now a days[1-2]. There are many Multi Inverter Topologies are being used. In this paper Neutral Point Clamped MultilevelInverter topology have been adopted[3-4].This paper proposes a basic circuit of Solar PV arrays and DC-DC boost converter which has been developed in SIMSCAPE library of MATLAB .The advantage of SIPSCAPE is that it provides better realistic modeling of physical component.

Solar Arrays have been simulated in SIMSCAPE library for different insolation and temperature condition which has been simulated for different values of load resistor so that the effect of load variations can be analyzed easily for developing the proper designing of boost converter. The DC to DC or boost converter is the second component connected between the PV system and the load.

3.SYSTEM COMPONENT MODELING

3.1PV System Characteristic and Modeling

The output of PV cell is a function of photon current that can be also determined by load current depending upon the solar insolation during its operation equation.[1]

Fig. 1. Electrical equivalent circuit of a PV cell

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V - R_s I}{N \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right] - I_{02} \left[\exp\left(\frac{V - R_s I}{N_2 \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V - R_s I}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

Thus PV panel output is dependent on solar insolation and temperature. A two diode model has been given in ‘SIMSCAPE’ library of MATLAB and results or characteristic of solar cell have been obtained by simulation under different irradiation and temperature. Behavior of solar cell is also verified experimentally

Fig.3 shows the IV and PV characteristic of solar cell. Fig. 4 shows I-V Characteristic of Solar Cell with different insolation at 25°C. Fig.5 shows IV Characteristic of Solar Cell with 1000 W/m2 insolation at temperature equals to 00C, 300C and 600C. Fig. 6 shows PV Characteristic of Solar Cell with 1000 W/m2 insolation at temperature equals to 0°C, 30°C and 60°C and constant solar insolation i.e 1000 w/m2.

Fig .2. IV and PV characteristic of a solar cell

Fig. 3. I-V Characteristic of solar cell

Fig.4. IV characteristic of solar cell

Fig.5. PV characteristic of a solar cell

3.2 MPPT Algorithm

To make Operate PV system properly within its Maximum Power Point, whatever the Solar irradiation and module temperature varies, is certainly needed a MPPT to find its MPP and maintain the peak power. So this Strategy provides the values of voltage and current at which it will provide the maximum output power. For obtaining Maximum Power Point Several methods of MPPT has been proposed in literatureSurvey. In thisPaper Perturb &Observe (P&O) is implemented, which is easy to implement and it is being used commercial PV power system. The flow chart of P&O method is presented below[14]

Fig.6. Flow Chart Of P&O algorithm

3.3 Designing of Boost Converter

The DC-DC converter has mainly two modes, both are being used as their own purpose. CCM is being used for efficient power conversion and discontinuous conduction mode is mainly used for low power or stand by operation.[1]

Fig.7. Electrical equivalent circuit DC-DC Boost Converter

3-3-1 Continuous Conduction Mode

(a) Mode1($0 \leq t \leq t_{on}$)

Fig.8. equivalent circuit Boost Converter for CCM For $0 \leq t \leq t_{on}$

Mode 1 begins when MOSFET is switched on at $t=0$. The equivalent circuit is shown in figure. When it is on the inductor current is greater than zero and it will ramp up linearly. The equivalent circuit for mode 1 has been shown in figure given below.

(b) Mode-2 ($t_{on} \leq t \leq t_{off}$)

Fig.9. equivalent circuit of boost Converter for ($t_{on} \leq t \leq t_{off}$)

Mode 2 starts when MOSFET is switched off at $t=t_{on}$ and terminates at $t=t_{off}$. Equivalent circuit for Mode 2 has been shown in the above figure. The inductor current decreases in this mode until the MOSFET is turn on for the next cycle.

$$V_{in}t_{on} + (V_{in} - V_{out})t_{off} = 0 \quad (2)$$

The equation for Duty cycle of the converter is given below

$$D = 1 - \frac{v_{in} \times \eta}{v_{out}} \quad (3)$$

3.4 Selection of Semiconductor Devices

The selection of semiconductor should be done in such a way so that it can withstand the worst case voltage and current the maximum voltage of solar PV will be the maximum voltage stress for the switch.

$$V_{\max, stress} = V_{pv, \max} \quad (4)$$

Maximum current stress will take place only when system power is predominately provided by PV system.

$$I_{PEAK} = I_{OUTPUT} + I_{RIPPL} \quad (5)$$

$$I_{PEAK} = \frac{P_{in, \max}}{V_{pv}} + \frac{\Delta * P_{in, \max}}{V_{pv}} \quad (6)$$

1-Selection of inductor

It should be ensured that coil should have low dc resistance. Selection of inductor should be done on the basis so that it allows the maximum ripple current at minimum duty cycle D. Boost inductor value can determined by the following equation [1]

$$L = \frac{v_{in} \times (v_{out} - v_{in})}{\Delta I_L \times F_S \times V_{out}} \quad (7)$$

2-Selection of Capacitor

The value of capacitor should be chosen in such a way so that its ESR should be minimum.. Lower ESR will also minimize the ripple in output voltage.[1]

An approximate equation for determining the value of capacitance is given below.

$$C_{out} = \frac{I_{out(max)} \times D}{F_s \times \Delta V_{out}} \quad (8)$$

3.5 Neutral Point Clamped Multilevel Inverter Modeling

Now a day’s multilevel inverters are gaining more attention due to its popularity and has been become more popular with less disturbances and it can easily operate at lower switching frequencies than ordinary two-level inverters .Regulated Dc voltage from the boost converter goes to NPCMLI and it converts the dc into ac waveform consisting of multiple level according to its modeling. The advantage of MLI over two level inverter is that it consist of multiple level and hence increasing the level will reduced THD , stress on device. fig(11) shows the modeling of basic 5 level neutral Point clamped MultiLevel Inverter and Table no(1) shows the switching State of NPCMLI inverter .

Fig. 10 . Electrical equivalent circuit DC-DC Boost Converter

Switch State								Output Volt (Va0)	Output Volt (Van)
SA1	SA2	SA3	SA4	SA1'	SA2'	SA3'	SA4'		
1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	V_{DC}	$V_{DC}/2$
0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	$3V_{DC}/4$	$V_{DC}/4$
0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	$V_{DC}/4$	0
0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	$V_{DC}/2$	$-V_{DC}/4$
0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	$-V_{DC}/2$

Table.1 Switching state of 5level NPCMLI

4.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.11. MATLAB Simulink and Simscape model of solar interfaced NPCMLI

Fig.12. Basic modelling of Solar cell In SIMSCAPE Library of MATLAB

The proposed system and its control strategy are designed and developed in Simulink library of MATLAB. and the behavior of the system have been observed under different varying Condition. Fig (a) and fig (b) shows the IV and PV characteristic of 1 module **SanyoHIP-225HDE1**.

Fig (c) and fig(d) shows the IV and PV characteristic of Array SanyoHIP-225HDE1 and from PV characteristic we can see that maximum power can be obtained at voltage=33.9volt and corresponding to this voltage the maximum power of the array is around 1.12kw.

Fig. 13(a).IV characteristic of one Module SanyoHIP-225HDE1

Fig 13(b) PV Characteristic of one Module

Fig. 14(a). IV Characteristic of Array Module SanyoHIP-225HDE1

Fig. 14(b) PV Characteristic of Array

Fig(a) shows the solar irradiation Figure (b) shows the power generation of solar PV arrays under different Solar irradiation . As we can see from the fig (b)TheMppt is enabled at 0.2 second.and after 0.2 second it is tracking the maximum power of solar PV arrays corresponding to its irradiation. Figure(c) Shows the variation in Duty Cycle just to maintain the output Voltage constant with under variable input PV array voltage and at .2 second variation in duty cycle corresponds to Maximum power. Figure(d) shows the variation in Generated PV Array Voltage(vp_v) Due to variation in Solar Irradiation And temperature .. Figure(e) shows the output Volatge(V_{boost}) of the boost converter.

Fig. 15(a)Solar irradiance in W/m2

Fig.15(b). Output power of PV panel with respect to Solar irradiance

Fig. 15(c). Duty Cycle of DC-DC converter to get MPP

Figure15(d). PV panel output Voltage with Respect to Solar irradiance

Figure 15(e) Shows the output voltage of boost converter

Fig17(a)18fig(a)fig19(a)fig20(a)fig21(a) shows the 3level, 5 level , 7level , 9level , 11 level voltage across load and fig17(b)18fig(b)19fig(b)fig20(b)fig21(b)shows the FFT analysis of the 3level 5level 7level 9level 11level. As we can see for figure as the number of levels are increasing the voltage profile is also improving and THD across the load is being improved.

Figure 16(a). shows the 3level output voltage across the load

Figure 16(b). shows the FFT analysis of 3 level Voltage

Figure17(a) shows the 5 level output voltage across the load

Figure17(b). shows the FFT analysis of 5 level Voltage

Figure 18(a)shows the 7 level output voltage across the load

Figure18(b)shows the FFT analysis of 7 level voltage

Figure 19(a) shows the 9-level output voltage across the load

Figure 19(b) shows the FFT analysis of 9 level

Figure 20(a) shows the output 11-level output voltage across the load

Figure20(b) shows the FFT analysis of 11 level

Figure21. shows Comparison between THD and levels

5.CONCLUSION

The power conditioning is an essential stage for solar PV system. The output Voltage of PV is not sufficient for most of single phase application that's why power buffer i.e. DC-DC conversion stage is playing most crucial role. In case of solar PV application as well as in case of Maximum power Point tracking DC-DC conversion stage is most essential part of the system. In This paper NPCMLI interactive Solar System has been done. The proposed system can be implemented to reduce the THD as we know that the reduction of THD is the Main concern while using the power conditioning devices. It having the advantage of reduced harmonics, switching losses, lower rating for switches, reduction in THD reduced size and cost of filter. So application where high power required it serves as a good topology to be interfaced.

APPENDIX

PV Panel Parameters:

Module Type	SANIOHIP225HDE1
No of cells per Module	60
No of series connected Module/string	1
No of parallel string	5

Module Specification under STC

Parameters	Rating
N_c	60
N_p	50Khz
V_{oc}	41.79V
I_{sc}	7.13Amp
V_{mp}	33.9V
I_{mp}	6.63Amp
R_c	.02Ohm
I_{nh}	7.145Amp
T_r	25 ⁰ c
S	1000W / cm ²
I_D	0.002
I_{sat}	3.149e ⁻⁸

Boost Converter Parameter

Parameters	Rating
f_r	50Khz
f_c	100Khz
m_a	0.87
V_s	650 V

Parameters	Rating
f_s	100Khz
C	3.605e ⁻⁴ F
L	8.0125e ⁻⁴ H

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